

The influence of transformational leadership and organizational culture on employee performance at pt. Bank rakyat Indonesia (Persero) TBK. Gorontalo branch

Masnia H. Inombi *, Ismet Sulila and Juriko Abdussamad

Master of Public Administration Study Program, Gorontalo State University, Indonesia.

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the effect of transformational leadership and organizational culture on employee performance at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch partially or simultaneously. The approach in this research is quantitative. This research uses the *expost facto* method and correlational research design. Data collection through questionnaires, interviews, observation, and documentation. The data analysis technique used is multiple regression. The results showed that (1) transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch by 30.80%. The better and ideal transformational leadership style applied by the leadership will improve employee performance at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch. (2) Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch by 54.00%. The more conducive the culture in an organization, the more employee performance will increase in quantity, quality, and timeliness of work. (3) Transformational leadership and organizational culture together have a positive and significant effect on employee performance at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch by 84.80%. The influence of other variables is employee competence, leadership supervision, education and training, employee career management, and compensation.

Keywords: Organizational Culture; Employee Performance; Transformational Leadership; Influence

1. Introduction

Success in achieving performance cannot be separated from the efforts of employees in carrying out their vision and realizing their mission. As stated by Dessler (2013), Shane and Glinow (2010), and Goonewardena (2017), the presence of leaders will influence and motivate organizational members to contribute to achieving goals.

Goonewardena (2017: 1) says leadership style and behavior have a positive influence on employee performance. Observing this description, the researcher interprets that each individual has a different leadership style, which later, the leadership style will also affect employee performance. One of the leadership styles that can stimulate and inspire employees is the transformational leadership style.

Another factor that can stimulate the performance of an employee is the norms and culture in the organization. Deal and Kennedy (in Alvesson 2012: 43) suggest that a strong organizational culture will encourage and improve employee performance. In line with Deal and Kennedy, Denison (1991: 203) says that organizational culture as the key to organizational change improves its performance. Corporate organizations that have maximum performance not only lie in a strong culture but also appear to have a strong internal and external focus as well.

* Corresponding author: Masnia H. Inombi

As one of the State-Owned Enterprises (BUMN) companies, PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch is required to have optimal performance and continue to evaluate the performance of its employees. Based on the results of preliminary observations, it is known that the performance of BRI Gorontalo Branch marketing employees has decreased. This can be seen from the absence of marketing employees who received excellent predicates from 2019 to 2021. From the data obtained, in 2019, out of 64 marketing employees, employees who received excellent criteria were 15.63%, good category was 65.62%, fair category was 10.94%, and unfavorable category was 7.81%. In 2020, employees who received excellent criteria were 12.50%, the good category was 78.13%, the fair category was 6.25%, and the unfavorable category was 3.12%. In 2021, employees who received excellent criteria were 10.94%, the good category was 89.06%, the fair category was 0%, and the unfavorable category was 0%.

Based on the phenomenon stated, the researcher considers it necessary to conduct research on employee performance. Thus, researchers are encouraged to conduct research with the title "The Effect of Transformational Leadership and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (PERSERO) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch." This study will examine and examine how the influence of transformational leadership and organizational culture on employee performance at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch. This research is directed at the performance of marketing employees who handle business loans at BRI Units in the Gorontalo Branch office because BRI Units have been considered to be the largest contributor to the performance of PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia Tbk.

2. Methods

This research was conducted at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch with the object of research is the performance achievement data of each employee. The approach in this research is quantitative. This research uses the *expost facto* method and correlational research design. Data collection was done through the distribution of questionnaires, interviews, observation, and documentation. The data analysis technique used is multiple regression analysis.

3. Results

3.1. Descriptive Analysis of Research Variables

3.1.1. Variable of transformational leadership

The results of descriptive analysis for transformational leadership variables in this study are presented as follows:

Table 1 Descriptive Results of Transformational Leadership Variable

No.	Statement Score			Indicator Score	Criteria	
	Actual	Ideal	%		Statement	Indicator
X1-1	196	230	85.22%	81.57%	Good Enough	Good Enough
X1-2	195	230	84.78%		Good	
X1-3	189	230	82.17%		Good Enough	
X1-4	177	230	76.96%		Good Enough	
X1-5	181	230	78.70%		Good Enough	
X1-6	177	230	76.96%	78.87%	Good Enough	Good Enough
X1-7	173	230	75.22%		Good Enough	
X1-8	183	230	79.57%		Good Enough	
X1-9	184	230	80.00%		Good Enough	
X1-10	190	230	82.61%		Good Enough	
X1-11	192	230	83.48%	83.74%	Good Enough	Good Enough
X1-12	195	230	84.78%		Good	

X1-13	187	230	81.30%		Good Enough	
X1-14	196	230	85.22%		Good	
X1-15	193	230	83.91%		Good Enough	
X1-16	192	230	83.48%	81.65%	Good Enough	Good Enough
X1-17	176	230	76.52%		Good Enough	
X1-18	185	230	80.43%		Good Enough	
X1-19	192	230	83.48%		Good Enough	
X1-20	194	230	84.35%		Good	
Total	3,747	4,600	81.46%	Good Enough		

Source: Excel Data Processing, 2023

Based on the results in Table 1, the overall percentage of achievement scores for transformational leadership variables is 81.46% which is in the "good enough" category.

3.1.2. Variable of organizational culture

The results of descriptive analysis for organizational culture variables in this study are presented as follows:

Table 2 Descriptive Results of Organizational Culture Variable

No.	Statement Score			Indicator Score	Criteria	
	Actual	Ideal	%		Statement	Indicator
X2.1	195	230	84.78%	85.22%	Good	Good
X2.2	197	230	85.65%		Good	
X2.3	202	230	87.83%		Good	
X2.4	196	230	85.22%		Good	
X2.5	190	230	82.61%		Good Enough	
X2.6	195	230	84.78%	84.70%	Good	Good
X2.7	187	230	81.30%		Good Enough	
X2.8	194	230	84.35%		Good	
X2.9	197	230	85.65%		Good	
X2.10	201	230	87.39%		Good	
X2.11	196	230	85.22%	83.65%	Good	Good Enough
X2.12	202	230	87.83%		Good	
X2.13	183	230	79.57%		Good Enough	
X2.14	193	230	83.91%		Good Enough	
X2.15	188	230	81.74%		Good Enough	
X2.16	194	230	84.35%	84.70%	Good	Good
X2.17	190	230	82.61%		Good Enough	
X2.18	193	230	83.91%		Good Enough	
X2.19	198	230	86.09%		Good	
X2.20	199	230	86.52%		Good	
Total	3,890	4,600	84.57%	Good		

Source: Excel Data Processing, 2023

Based on Table 2, the overall percentage of achievement scores for organizational culture variables is 84.57% which is in the "good" category.

3.1.3. Variable of employee performance

The results of descriptive analysis for employee performance variables in this study are presented as follows:

Table 3 Descriptive Results of Employee Performance Variables

No.	Statement Score			Indicator Score	Criteria	
	Actual	Ideal	%		Statement	Indicator
Y1	188	230	81.74%	83.65%	Good Enough	Good Enough
Y2	199	230	86.52%		Good	
Y3	182	230	79.13%		Good Enough	
Y4	194	230	84.35%		Good	
Y5	199	230	86.52%		Good	
Y6	194	230	84.35%	85.74%	Good	Good
Y7	199	230	86.52%		Good	
Y8	200	230	86.96%		Good	
Y9	194	230	84.35%		Good	
Y10	199	230	86.52%		Good	
Y11	197	230	85.65%	83.91%	Good	Good Enough
Y12	196	230	85.22%		Good	
Y13	199	230	86.52%		Good	
Y14	180	230	78.26%		Good Enough	
Y15	193	230	83.91%		Good Enough	
Y16	183	230	79.57%	82.43%	Good Enough	Good Enough
Y17	182	230	79.13%		Good Enough	
Y18	190	230	82.61%		Good Enough	
Y19	198	230	86.09%		Good	
Y20	195	230	84.78%		Good	
Total	3,861	4,600	83.93%	Good Enough		

Source: Excel Data Processing, 2023

Based on Table 3, the overall percentage of achievement scores for employee performance variables is 83.93% which is in the "good enough" category.

3.2. Multiple Regression Equation and Partial Test

The results of multiple regression analysis with the help of the SPSS program are shown in Table 4 as follows:

Table 4 Regression Analysis Results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-17.651	4.862		-3.630	0.001
	TransformationalLeadership	0.470	0.087	0.399	5.407	0.000
	OrganizationalCulture	0.721	0.085	0.626	8.469	0.000

Source: SPSS 21 processed data, 2023

Based on the analysis results in Table 4, the multiple linear regression equation model is:

$$\hat{Y} = -17,651 + 0,470X_1 + 0,721X_2 + \varepsilon$$

Based on the results of the analysis, the partial test results in this study can be described:

- Partial test interpretation of transformational leadership variables

Based on the analysis, the t-count value for the transformational leadership variable is obtained at 5.407 while the t-value for the t-table is 1.989. If the two t values are compared, the t-count value is still greater than the t-table value ($5.407 > 1.989$). The t-count significance value for the transformational leadership variable is 0.000. The significance value of transformational leadership is smaller than the probability value of 0.05, or the value ($0.000 < 0.05$), then H_a is accepted. It can be concluded that transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch.

- Interpretation of partial test of organizational culture variables

Based on the analysis, the t-count value for the organizational culture variable is obtained at 8.469 while the t-value for the t-table is 1.989. If the two t values are compared, the t-count value is still greater than the t-table value ($8.469 > 1.989$). The significance value of the t-count for the organizational culture variable is 0.000. The significance value of organizational culture is smaller than the probability value of 0.05, or the value ($0.000 < 0.05$), then H_a is accepted. It can be concluded that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch.

3.2.1. Simultaneous Testing Results (F Test)

The results of simultaneous testing with the help of the SPSS 21 program are shown in table 5 below:

Table 5 Simultaneous Testing Results

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	7840.485	2	3920.242	120.196	0.000 ^b
	Residual	1402.457	43	32.615		
	Total	9242.942	45			

Source: SPSS 21 processed data, 2023

Based on the table above, the F-count value of this study is 120.196 with a significance value or probability of 0.000. Meanwhile, the value of the F-table at a significant level of 5% df_1 of $k = 2$ and df_2 of $N - k - 1 = 46 - 2 - 1 = 43$ is 3.108. If these two F values are compared, then the F-calculated value obtained is much greater than the F-table. Then the probability value obtained from the test is smaller than the α value of 0.05. Overall, it can be concluded that transformational leadership and organizational culture together have a significant effect on employee performance at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch.

3.2.2. Testing the Coefficient of Determination

To find out the magnitude of the coefficient of determination (R^2) can be seen in Table 6 below:

Table 6 Coefficient of Determination

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.921 ^a	0.848	0.841	5.71098

Source: SPSS 21 processed data, 2023

Based on the results of the coefficient of determination analysis in the table above, it shows that the coefficient of determination or the *R-Square* number is 0.848. This value indicates that 84.80% of the variability of employee performance at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch can be explained by transformational leadership and organizational culture, while the remaining 15.20% can be explained by other variables not examined in this study. Furthermore, the partial coefficient test was carried out. The test results for the partial determination coefficient are described in the form of the following table:

Table 7 Partial Determination Coefficient

Model	Standardized Coefficients	Correlation	Determination	
			Value	%
Transformational leadership	0.399	0.771	0.308	30.80%
Organizational culture	0.626	0.863	0.540	54.00%
Simultaneous Coefficient of Determination				

Source: SPSS 21 processed data, 2023

Based on the results of the coefficient of determination analysis above, it can be explained for the influence of each variable as follows:

3.3. Transformational leadership

As much as 30.80% of the ability of the transformational leadership variable in influencing employee performance at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch.

3.4. Culture of organization

Around 54.00% of the ability of organizational culture variables in influencing employee performance at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch.

4. Discussion

4.1. The Effect of Transformational Leadership on Employee Performance

The results of descriptive testing found that the overall percentage of the achievement score for the transformational leadership variable was 81.46% which was in the "good enough" category. This shows that transformational leadership at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch can reach a higher level so that it can have a greater positive impact on employee motivation and performance, while also helping achieve the company's goals and vision more effectively. Transformational leaders have a strong positive influence on employees, building trusting and supportive relationships. Management at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch can strengthen positive influence by being a good role model, communicating effectively, and providing constructive feedback to employees.

The results for each indicator for the transformational leadership variable at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch is described as follows:

4.2. Idealized influence

Idealized Influence is at a good criterion, meaning that idealized influence reflects how leaders behave as ideal role models for their team members. Leaders who have idealized influence demonstrate high integrity, strong work ethics,

and consistent morality. They create trust and respect from team members by demonstrating dedication to organizational values and commitment to achieving common goals.

4.3. Inspirational motivation

Inspirational motivation is in the good criteria, meaning that Inspirational Motivation reflects the leader's ability to communicate an inspiring vision and inspire fighting spirit among team members. Inspirational leaders can articulate clear goals and direction, and they use effective communication to motivate team members to work hard to achieve those goals.

4.4. Intellectual stimulation

Intellectual stimulation is at a fairly good criterion, meaning that intellectual stimulation includes the leader's ability to stimulate critical thinking and innovation among team members. Leaders who implement intellectual stimulation challenge team members to think outside the box, ask challenging questions, and encourage the exploration of new ideas. This helps to increase creativity and problem-solving ability within the team.

4.5. Individualized consideration

Individualized consideration is at a good criterion, meaning that individualized consideration reflects the care and attention given by leaders to the individual needs and aspirations of team members. Leaders who practice individualized consideration actively listen and provide support to team members, help them overcome obstacles, and assist in their professional development. This creates a strong relationship between the leader and team members, thereby increasing the sense of engagement and work motivation.

The results of testing the first hypothesis with multiple regression analysis found that transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch with a coefficient of determination of 30.80%. The better and ideal transformational leadership style applied by the leadership will improve employee performance at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch. Transformational leaders encourage innovation and creativity among employees. By providing intellectual stimulus, such as encouraging open discussions, giving freedom to try new approaches, and rewarding innovative ideas, transformational leaders create an environment that supports the development of new ideas. This can improve work quality, efficiency, and introduce significant improvements in company operations.

The results of this study are in line with the statement from Robbins and Judge (2014) through an explanation of the characteristics of the transformational leadership style stating that transformational leaders can stimulate employee performance creativity to a higher level. Sidik and Sutoyo (2020) in their research showed that both partially and simultaneously transformational leadership style has a significant influence on employee performance. Furthermore, the research of Rejeki, et al. (2020) said that partially transformational leadership has a significant effect and is the most dominant variable affecting performance.

4.6. The Effect of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance

The results of descriptive testing found that the overall percentage of achievement scores for organizational culture variables was 84.57% which was in the "good" category. This shows that management at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch can improve organizational culture by clarifying the expected values and ensuring the suitability of these values with the company's goals and vision. The application of these values must be consistent and visible in daily actions, both by management and employees. A healthy organizational culture recognizes and rewards employee contributions. Management can improve a culture of appreciation by providing constructive feedback, rewarding regularly, and creating recognition programs that reinforce employees' sense of pride and job satisfaction.

The results for each indicator for the organizational culture variable at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch is described as follows:

4.7. Engagement

Engagement is at a fairly good criterion, meaning that engagement refers to the extent to which employees are emotionally and cognitively involved in their work. Transformational leaders who are able to create a supportive work environment and pay attention to employees' needs can increase their level of engagement. High engagement can increase employees' motivation, productivity, and sense of responsibility for their work.

4.8. Consistency

Consistency is in the good criteria, meaning that consistency refers to the leader's ability to be consistent and reliable in their behavior and decisions. Consistent transformational leaders build trust and confidence from team members. They follow their values and commitments with consistent actions, creating a stable and reliable environment in the workplace.

4.9. Adaptability

Adaptability is at a fairly good criterion, meaning that Adaptability reflects the leader's ability to adapt to changes and challenges that arise in a changing business environment. Adaptive transformational leaders are able to face challenges with creativity and innovation. They can also help team members adapt to changes and maintain balance in different situations.

4.10. Mission

Mission is at a fairly good criterion, meaning that mission refers to how transformational leaders can articulate the vision and mission of the organization clearly and convincingly. Leaders who have a clear and strong mission can inspire team members to contribute and focus on a common goal. A strong mission also helps create organizational identity and cohesion.

The results of testing the second hypothesis with multiple regression analysis found that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch with a coefficient of determination of 54.00%. The more conducive the organizational culture in an organization, the performance of employees at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch will be of higher quality in terms of quantity, quality, and timeliness of work. A positive organizational culture encourages collaboration and cooperation among employees. Employees at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch will work together in teams, share knowledge, experience, and skills, and support each other. Effective collaboration increases productivity, creativity, and quality of work, which ultimately has a positive impact on individual performance and overall team performance.

These results are in accordance with the statement from Robbins and Judge (2014) that organizational culture is an important factor in increasing organizational effectiveness. Organizational culture can be a major competitive advantage instrument when organizational culture can support organizational strategy and answer or overcome environmental challenges quickly and appropriately. Organizational culture can affect performance, the better the organizational culture, the better the employee performance, on the contrary, the worse the organizational culture, the lower the employee performance. According to the results of research conducted by Sidik and Sutoyo (2020) and Rejeki, et al. (2020), partially organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

4.10.1. The Effect of Transformational Leadership and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance

Descriptive testing results found that the overall percentage of achievement scores for employee performance variables was 83.93% which was in the "good enough" category. This shows that employees at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch have succeeded in achieving most of the goals and performance indicators set. They have performed the expected tasks and achieved an adequate level of productivity. Although employee performance is considered "good enough", there is still room for improvement and enhancement. Management at the Gorontalo branch can continue to encourage and support employees to achieve better performance levels by providing the necessary training, feedback, and support. Thus, employee performance can be continuously improved to reach higher levels.

The results for each indicator for the employee performance variable at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch is described as follows:

4.10.2. Quality of work

Work quality is in fairly good criteria, meaning that the quality of work of employees of PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch is influenced by several factors, such as their competence and skills in carrying out the tasks at hand. In addition, a supportive work environment and adequate training can improve the quality of employee work. Leadership that facilitates open communication and provides constructive feedback can also contribute to improving work quality.

4.10.3. Quantity of work

Work quantity is in fairly good criteria, meaning that the work quantity of employees of PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch is related to employee productivity in completing assigned tasks and projects. Efficiency in the work process and good time management can help increase work quantity. In addition, appropriate motivation and incentives can encourage employees to achieve the set quantity targets.

4.10.4. Work effectiveness

Work effectiveness is in fairly good criteria, meaning that work effectiveness includes the ability of employees of PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch in achieving predetermined goals. Factors such as a clear understanding of work objectives, efficient use of resources, and the ability to complete tasks effectively can contribute to employee work effectiveness.

4.10.5. Independence

Independence is in fairly good criteria, meaning that the independence of employees of PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch relates to their ability to take initiative and be responsible for their tasks without always having to be directed or supervised by superiors. Employees who have autonomy in their work tend to feel more motivated and feel greater responsibility for the results of their work.

The results of testing the third hypothesis with multiple regression analysis found that transformational leadership and organizational culture together have a positive and significant effect on employee performance at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch. The influence of other variables is as stated by Moenir (2002: 88), Irmalasari and Mayesti (2017) and Rolando (2018: 56), namely employee competence, leadership supervision, education and training, employee career management and compensation.

This is in accordance with the opinion of Rejeki, et al. (2020) and Perdana (2020). They concluded that transformational leadership style, work motivation, and organizational culture simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Through the adoption of strong transformational leadership and a positive organizational culture, it can create a work environment that motivates and supports employees to achieve their best potential. Employees will feel inspired, engaged, and have high involvement in their work. This positive impact will be reflected in increased productivity, work quality, team collaboration, innovation, and employee satisfaction and retention. Thus, transformational leadership and positive organizational culture are key factors in improving employee performance.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of the research and discussion, the following conclusions are presented:

Transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch by 30.80%. The better and ideal transformational leadership style applied by the leadership will improve employee performance at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch.

Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch by 54.00%. The more conducive the organizational culture in an organization, the performance of employees at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch will be more qualified in terms of quantity, quality and timeliness of work.

Transformational leadership and organizational culture together have a positive and significant effect on employee performance at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch by 84.80%. The influence of other variables, namely employee competence variables, leadership supervision, education and training, employee career management and compensation.

Suggestion

Based on the research conclusions, the following research suggestions are made:

We recommend that the leadership and management of PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Cabang Gorontalo evaluates the transformational leadership applied in the Gorontalo branch by understanding the principles of transformational leadership and applying them in daily practice.

We recommend that the leadership and management of PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch builds a positive and supportive organizational culture and creates an inclusive and mutually supportive work environment. Then, build a reward and recognition program that strengthens a positive organizational culture for good performance.

We recommend that employees of PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Gorontalo Branch develop leadership and transformational skills, build a proactive and collaborative attitude by developing good communication skills to strengthen interactions with fellow employees and management. Then maintain enthusiasm and motivation and look for opportunities to take on new responsibilities or challenging tasks to stay motivated and develop in achieving performance that has good progress.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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